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through Literary,
Cultural and Folkloric
Approaches

Chief Editor
Dr. Dipak Jyoti Baruah

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**A REFEREED (PEER-REVIEWED) BI-ANNUAL NATIONAL RESEARCH
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CONTENTS

- Editorial #7
- A Study of Disability in Mahesh Dattani's *Tara* and Arundhati Roy's *God of Small Things* #9
Navdeep Kaur
- Beyond Deficits: Depiction of Neurodivergent Identities in Elle McNicoll's *Own Voices Fiction : Show Us Who You Are* #14
Sonima. K. K.
- Beyond the Binary: Exploring Hegemonic Masculinity and Disability in Bengali Short Stories #19
Dr. Avijit Pramanik
- 'Crippling' Disability and Reclaiming Space and Beauty: A Study of Keah Brown's *The Pretty One* #24
Mahima Dahiya, Rekha Rani
- 'Crippling Up' in Indian Popular Media: An Ethical and Representational Question #28
Dr. Sharada Devi V, Dr. Sajna Sanal
- Deconstruction of the Social Misunderstanding of Cerebral Palsy (CP) in the Society, in Relevance with Folktale Culture #33
Yasmin Nasima Parvin
- Disability and Humour: Analysing the Co-existence of Tragedy and Comedy #39
Prachi Behrani, Dr. Vinaya Kumari, Dr. Beulah Victor
- Disability and the Master-Slave Narrative in the Early Novels of William Golding #44
Bishnupada Ray, Prof. Pradip Kumar Patra
- Disability In Zadie Smith's *White Teeth* #48
Siddharth Sharma
- Disabled Female Characters and the Victorian Ideals of 'Normalcy': A Reading of Dinah Craik's *Olive* and Harriet Martineau's *Deerbrook* #53
Manab Medhi
- Disabled Gender: Relocating the meaning of 'Disable' in the context of Tsitsi Dangarembga's *Nervous Conditions* #58
Navdeep Kaur Kalsi
- Elucidating Challenges of Bipolar Disorder in Shreevatsa Nevatia's *How To Travel Light* #62
Aditi Bhardwaj, Dr. Anupriya Roy Srivastava
- Exploring Disability and Resilience: Countering and Curbing the Barriers of Inclusion in Firdaus Kanga's *Trying to Grow* #67
Manisha
- Disease, Disability, and Desire: A Study of Select Western Romantic Films of 2010s #72
Bikram Chowdhury

Disease, Disability, and Desire: A Study of Select Western Romantic Films of 2010s

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Abstract

This research article talks about how disability is displayed in relation to disease and desire in film texts. It attempts to show how disease, disability, and desire interact with and influence one another in the lives of the patients characterized in the films titled *The Fault in Our Stars*(2014), *Midnight Sun* (2018), and *Five Feet Apart* (2019). By foregrounding that disability of living a normal social life is an integral component of disease for the patients in the physical level as well as the psychological level, the paper will explore how society has encoded normative behaviours of the patients, and in what ways the patients respond to this societal normativity when it comes to fulfilling of their desires. In Freudian terms, how the norms connected to disease and disability delineate the 'superego' of the patients, and how this superego aids in taming/or even honing their 'Id' and 'eros' for living life to the lees, will also be examined in this paper with substantial reference to the films mentioned above.

Keywords: Disease, disability, desire, romantic films, western films

Disease has been an integral part of human lives throughout the history of humankind. Disease can be located both as an external and an internal factor of human corporeality, affecting the daily lives of the diseased by somewhat 'disabling' the daily normal activities of life. Disability of living a 'normal' life thus becomes a significant part of the lives of the diseased, as they feel or are made to feel 'disabled' from participating in some essential daily activities of life. This state of being/ feeling 'disabled' results in the metaphorical death of 'desires' that are also essential to human life. The physical disability resulting from

diseases is coupled with the psychological disability that comes to the fore as a societal norm. The interconnectedness among these 3Ds, i.e., disease, disability, and desire, can be located in real life as well as reel life. This paper basically deals with how the following films *The Fault in Our Stars* (2014), *Midnight Sun* (2018), and *Five Feet Apart* (2019) display the complexities among these notions of disease, disability, and desire.

This research paper mainly focuses on the protagonists of these films, irrespective of gender, who are presented as 'physically diseased or socially disabled' individuals. The selected films will be studied through the lens of Freudian theories. On the one hand, these theories include the concepts of Id, Ego, and Superego which will be applied in the film texts in order to explicate the complex structures of norms of the society as a defining/ delimiting factor of the desires and drives of the patients. (Freud 22) On the other hand, there are the concepts of Eros and Thanatos which will be used to describe the life drives and death drives of the patients. (36) Seclusion and solitariness in the lives of patients bring about an inwardness in their lifestyle which works as a setback in their social life. Disease, therefore, becomes a kind of 'superego' which demarcates the 'id' and 'ego' of the patients. Thus, the life force, also known as 'eros', of the patients is tamed by the dis-'ease' that they suffer from. Disease comes not only as a physical barrier to fulfilling desires but as a social establishment that keeps

the patients from even 'desiring' a normal life. The 'normal' becomes an abnormality because the patients with certain diseases get labelled as vulnerable. This agreed vulnerability makes the patients look like partly 'disabled' individuals who 'deserve' to live a secluded life away from society. These intricacies among disease, disability, and desire can well be located in the films.

Disease is a pathological condition that attacks the "corporeal frame" of human beings in a mortal or semi-mortal way. Physical disease "disables" the patients from desiring the normative "divine drudgery" of daily lives. Disease-induced disability is both a mental and physical condition that makes it difficult for the person with disease to perform certain activities of daily life, participate in, and interact with the world around. In the film, *The Fault in Our Stars*, Hazel Grace, a cancer patient, hesitates to engage herself in the 'public sphere'. Normativity of the non-performance of the patients in daily activities is a socially constructed phenomenon. In a cancer support group, she meets and falls in love with another cancer patient namely, Augustus. The portrayal of Augustus' friend, Isaac is also noteworthy from this perspective because he also suffers from the issues of impending blindness. His not-yet disability becomes the main reason behind the fact that his girlfriend leaves him. The societal norms of maintaining a safe distance between the healthy and the diseased have been an established norm deeply rooted in society.

Similarly, in the films *Midnight Sun*, and *Five Feet Apart*, both the female protagonists have a rare physical condition respectively called xeroderma pigmentosum and cystic fibrosis. Stella Grant, the female protagonist of the former film, and Willy Newman, a similar patient with CF, eventually fell in love with each other. But they could not come closer to each other. At least a distance of six feet has to be maintained between the patients with CF. The hesitation of Hazel Grace to join the support group of similar patients, the alienation of Katie Price from the daytime outer world, and the OCD of Stella Grant work as a 'disabling' tool in their individual way to living a life of their own.

Disease acts as a driving force affecting the social lives of patients, thus making them look "introverted" as per the accepted codes of social behaviour. In the film *Midnight Sun*, Katie Price lives her childhood and adulthood thoroughly in seclusion, away from the 'light' of the world. Less engagement in the socialization process of the outside world can be seen as a tentative cause of her awkward conversational skills while talking to Charlie at the railway station. The awkwardness that was visible in her interaction with him might also have been a product of the fact that she saw the boy from her scopophilic window day in and day out, but the boy Charlie never saw her see him grow into the man that now he is.

Although disability is an apparent hindrance to the fulfilment of desire in the lives of patients, they sometimes surpass their limits of disability due to their immense life drive, i.e., eros. In *The Fault in Our Stars*, Hazel Grace, even though terminally ill, is desperate to visit Amsterdam in order to find the answers to her questions regarding the novel, titled *An Imperial Affliction*. The novelist Peter Van Houten ultimately disappoints her by being less interested in whatever he wrote in the past. Her curiosities find an absurd ending because the artist who created the art is no longer interested in that art. This absurdity becomes a spiritual crisis for her along with her boyfriend Augustus Waters. At the beginning of the film, Hazel Grace speaks of depression in a voiceover by saying, "Depression is not a side effect of cancer. It is a side effect of dying." (*The Fault in Our Stars* 00:01:35-00:01:43) For the patients with terminal diseases, death is not an object of abjection. Death becomes a desire for many patients who give up on their 'eros' for living life. Thanatotic elements in fantasizing about death in patients with diseases are a common sign of being terminally diseased.

The compulsory six feet "social distance" between Stella Grant and Willy Newman in *Five Feet Apart* is also a kind of disability that works as an alienating tool between Id and Superego. They mutually give themselves a one-foot discount in their six feet distance as a means to celebrate their amorous connection. Stella uploads a video where she revolts against CF by saying:

Shit, it's complicated to try to explain, but it's even hard to fall in love. After all CF has taken from me, from us, I don't mind stealing a little something back. One Foot. One fucking foot of space, of distance, of length or whatever you wanna call it. I don't mind stealing that back. (*Five Feet Apart* 00:57:06-00:57:33)

A believer in the *carpe-diem* philosophy of life, Will is a careless CF patient who shows no rigorous medical responsibility, whereas Stella Grant is a responsible patient with CF who manages her hygiene and performs her medical care religiously. In the last portion of the film, as a gesture of protest against CF, Will and Stella go outside to see the lights that Stella sees from the hospital. There he tries to give her CPR in order to save her from the cold that she has caught in the pool of ice. He bids her farewell assuming that she contracted *B. cepacia* while giving her CPR.

The film *Midnight Sun* is undoubtedly a saga of a tragic love story. Katie Price, a patient with XP, is a 'locked down' lady. Her scopophilic gaze toward Charlie, a man who passes by her house on a regular basis, made her fall in love with him without his knowledge of it. In a situational irony, when she was singing at a train station near her home, he approached her in between her singing with a desire to know her. But ironically, she knew him already. Her disease, which demanded her isolation and seclusion from the outer world for most of the time, did not let her meet him earlier mostly because of her illness, and partly because of her fear of being a burden to anyone outside her close circle. Gradually, when she started meeting with him frequently but only at night, they both fell in love. When Charlie asked to spend some time together with her, she said to him, "I am really busy during the day, but I could be free at night." (*Midnight Sun* 00:20:26-00:20:34) She did not want to reveal her disease to him at that time even after frequent suggestions from her father. Engaged so much in *eros*, one night while hopping around with Charlie at some beach, she lost track of time which neared sunrise. Her skin contracted UV rays that morning and her health started deteriorating. Her desire to have a happy

life with Charlie became a hopeless dream. In the very last period of the film, she went out into the sun fearlessly with Charlie and even watched Charlie win his swimming competition. At the expense of her life force, she attempted to dodge her disability of being in the sun, the light of the world due to the disease. Thus, she won over the superego of society which demands a particular behaviour of the patients.

In the film texts, there is a simultaneous representation of 'disease affected disabled life' in both the physical level and the mental level. Added to their physical disability which becomes a barrier to their 'normal' activities of life, the societal norms that precede the normative established behaviour of patients work as an apparatus to delimit their mental and physical activities in order to bind them in their depressive circles. A common ground among these three films is that the diseases force the characters to behave in a particular way that seems partly influenced by their physical conditions and the resulting social stigma. The diseases kind of disable them physically as well as mentally to perform day-to-day activities in a normal way.

In conclusion, it can be deduced that the relationship between disease, disability, and desire in the films is a multi-layered one. Although terminologically poles apart, they have a common space of existence simultaneously in a single being. As diseases in the bodies of the patients produce a certain kind of disability, disability projects a force of resistance against the concretions of any desires. As the paper has explored, it is no wonder that despite the societal norms and physical inabilities, the patients-protagonists-Hazel and Augustus in *The Fault in Our Stars*, Katie Price in *Midnight Sun*, Stella and Will in *Five Feet Apart*- rise above their restrictions, and search for ways to fulfil the urges of their id which were hitherto hidden due to the self/society-imposed superego. But their immense life drives have annihilated the barriers and limits of the superego. Ultimately, the patients driven by *Eros* defeat the psychological pressures of social obedience which involves behavioural conformities.

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